

THE BAD EFFECTS OF TOBACCO PRODUCTS ON THE BODY

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Annotation: Tobacco is also a risk factor for the development of cardiovascular diseases (40% of cases), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (80% of cases), malignant tumors (30% of cases, including 90% of cases of lung cancer). With tobacco abstinence, 40% of these diseases can be prevented.

Keywords: cardiovascular disease, tobacco products, diagnosis of tobacco addiction

Health risks of tobacco consumption:

- Respiratory tract — bronchitis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, lung cancer.
- Circulatory organs — increased pressure, accelerated pulse, narrowing of the arteries (gangrene), damage to the inner lining of the arteries (stroke, heart attack).
- Digestive organs — disorders of the stomach, stomach ulcers.
- Oral cavity — gum inflammation, oral cancer.
- Skin — rapid aging, grayness and pallor of the skin.
- Genitals — infertility, impotence.
- The human embryo is premature birth, underweight, poor health.
- The psyche is an addiction.
- General health — shortens the expected life span.

The effect of smoking on the oral cavity

Smoking leads to swelling and soreness of the gums, bleeding, and withdrawal of the gums from the base of the tooth, destruction and loss of teeth, taste sensitivity. 90% of cancers of the lips, tongue, pharynx, tonsils are directly related to tobacco consumption.

The effect of smoking on the heart and blood circulation

For a smoker, the risk of developing cardiovascular disease is 2-4 times higher than for a non-smoker. Tobacco consumption can lead to heart attack and stroke. Smoking causes peripheral blood supply disorders in the extremities. There are

painful spasms, numbness, goosebumps and a feeling of fatigue in the legs. Lack of blood supply increases the risk of infections, causes gangrene and the need for limb amputation.

The effect of smoking on the respiratory tract

The substances contained in tobacco smoke irritate the respiratory tract, reduce the elasticity of the lung tissue, destroy the walls of the pulmonary alveoli. 90% of lung cancer cases are associated with smoking. After a few days of quitting smoking, breathing improves, and the sense of smell and taste sharpen, after a few months, the smoker's cough disappears. Lung function improves not only by giving up conventional cigarettes, but also by giving up all other smoking tobacco products, including hookah.

The effect of smoking on the psyche

A person addicted to nicotine becomes irritable and restless without receiving the next dose of this substance in time. Gradually, memory and thinking begin to suffer. With the refusal of nicotine, brain function noticeably improves, cheerfulness increases, the ability to concentrate attention. Memory also improves, drowsiness and headaches disappear.

Smoking is a type of household drug addiction. For many smokers, smoking becomes part of their "I", and such an inner perception of oneself is sometimes very difficult to change.

However, smoking is more than a habit. All those forms of tobacco consumption that have become popular among the population contribute to the ingress of

nicotine into the blood. After the penetration of cigarette smoke into the lungs, nicotine enters the brain after seven seconds.

The inability to give up smoking is due to the already developed dependence of the body on the daily dose of nicotine. The body is waiting for this dose and requires it, as required proteins, fats and carbohydrates. Smokers have a different metabolism, some "nicotine addiction" has developed.

Trying to quit smoking, heavy smokers very often at first begin to feel not better, but much worse: cough, weakness, irritability, tendency to overeating increases, women are drawn to sweets, and in immoderate quantities.

The ignorance of society about this problem led to the idea of smoking as a "bad habit", in which the smoker was declared guilty because he could not stop smoking. However, the habit of smoking is formed only in 7-10% of people who regularly smoke tobacco. The remaining 90% are diagnosed with tobacco addiction.

People with a habit of smoking tobacco stop smoking on their own and do not need specialized medical care. Differential diagnosis of tobacco addiction and tobacco smoking habits is based on several clinical signs.

Most people are optimistic. Being healthy, they usually believe that they will always be accompanied by good health, and all sorts of diseases are the lot of other, weaker, susceptible to diseases people. But, alas, such optimism cannot be

considered justified if you do not take measures to prevent diseases, do not give up bad habits.

Cigarette smoke slowly erodes the health of the smoker. Scientists cite the following data: if tobacco tar is isolated from thousands of cigarettes, then up to 2 milligrams of a strong carcinogenic substance is found in it, which is quite enough to cause a malignant tumor in a rat or rabbit. If we take into account that a number of people smoke up to 40 cigarettes a day and even more, then in order to smoke a thousand cigarettes, they will need only 25 days.

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